

Fluorocerrates(IV) of Some Organic Base Cations and Hexamminecobalt(III) Cation

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The reactions of freshly precipitated $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$ dissolved in HF and organic bases, viz., pyridine (py), ethylenediamine (en), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), guanidine (gu) and biguanide (bigu), also dissolved in HF, yield $[\text{pyH}]_4[\text{H}_2\text{CeF}_6]$, $[\text{enH}_2][\text{CeF}_6]_2$, $[\text{2,2'-bipyH}_2][\text{H}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{F}_{11}]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{guH}][\text{H}_2\text{Ce}_2\text{F}_{11}]$ and $[\text{biguH}_2][\text{HCe}_2\text{F}_{11}]$. Similar reaction produces $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{CeF}_6]$. The TGA and ir spectra for the above compounds are reported and discussed.

VARIOUS fluorocerrates(IV) containing CeF_6^- , CeF_9^{2-} , CeF_9^{4-} ions and polynuclear fluoro ions, viz. Ce_2F_9^- , $\text{Ce}_2\text{F}_{11}^{2-}$, have been reported¹⁻⁵, but fluorocerrates with organic base cations are unknown. The preparation and study of some new fluorocerrates(IV) are described in this paper.

Experimental

Cerium in the fluorocerrates of organic base cations was estimated^{4,6} by igniting the compound at 1000° and weighing the residue as CeO_2 . The conversion of cerium in the above fluorocerrates into CeO_2 has been confirmed further⁷ through dissolving in H_2SO_4 , precipitating as $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$ and igniting to CeO_2 . In the case of hexamminecobalt(III) fluorocerrate the compound was fumed with conc. H_2SO_4 , $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$ was precipitated, filtered and ignited to CeO_2 and cobalt was estimated from the filtrate gravimetrically⁸ as CoSO_4 . For the estimation of fluorine, the compounds were fused with Na_2CO_3 , extracted with water and filtered. From the filtrate fluorine was estimated gravimetrically⁹ as PbClF . Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas' method.

For the preparation of a compound, freshly precipitated $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$ from ceric ammonium sulphate (0.5×10^{-2} mole) was dissolved in 10 ml HF (40%) followed by 90 ml water. A solution of organic base (except pyridine) dissolved in 10 ml HF (20%) was added dropwise to the above solution with mechanical stirring. The ratio of cerium : organic base was 1 : 1 for the ethylenediamine and bipyridyl compounds and 1 : 2 and 1 : 0.5 respectively, for the guanidine and biguanide compounds. Immediate precipitation occurred in each case. The compounds were filtered, washed with water and alcohol and filter-pressed. The hexamminecobalt(III) compound was also obtained as a precipitate in the above manner through the addition of hexamminecobalt(III) nitrate⁹. The compounds were dried in vacuum over KOH. In the case of pyridinium compound pyridine acidified with HF (20%) was added

in excess to the fluoro-cerium(IV) solution and the mixture was evaporated on water-bath. A turbidity appeared during concentration, which was rejected. The clear solution on concentration furnished needle-shaped crystals. The compound was filtered, washed with a little cold water and alcohol and pressed between filter papers. The analytical results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The fluorocerrates of protonated organic bases are colourless, while the hexamminecobalt(III) compound is pale yellow. Except the pyridinium compound others are stable at the room temperature. The pyridinium compound undergoes slow decomposition. On keeping the compound under vacuum over KOH and conc. H_2SO_4 , it decomposes progressively and the residue at the end of two months nearly corresponds to $[\text{pyH}][\text{Ce}_2\text{F}_9]$.

The fluorocerrates described above were obtained under almost identical conditions from relatively strong hydrofluoric acid solutions, but they belong to the various series of fluorocerrates as suggested from the analytical data. This is, however, not uncommon with fluorocompounds of heavier transition elements. The phenomenon suggests that various fluorocerrate(IV) species exist in equilibrium in solution and depending on the solubility, one or the other fluorocerrate(IV) species gets precipitated.

The TGA data of the compounds support the over-all composition of the compounds. The data of ethylenediaminium compound show a horizontal stretch at 230-270° corresponding to the formation of CeF_4 . This has been further confirmed by isothermal heating of the compound at 230°. The bipyridyl compound starts decomposing at 110°. Although horizontal stretches for the compound are noticed at 140-150, 210-250 and 260-310°, no stable intermediate including the anhydrous compound could be obtained through isothermal heating. The analysis of the residues at 450° obtained through

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF THE FLUOROCERRATES(IV) AND THEIR DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURES

Compound	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Decomp. Temp. °C
	Co	N	Ce	F	
(pyH) ₂ [H ₂ CeF ₆]	—	6.22 (6.16)	30.94 (30.83)	33.90 (33.45)	—
(enH ₂)[CeF ₆] ₂	—	5.17 (5.26)	53.71 (52.66)	36.69 (35.70)	160
(2,2'-bipyH ₂)[H ₂ Ce ₂ F ₁₁] ₂ ·2H ₂ O	—	2.39 (2.38)	48.21 (47.66)	35.37 (35.55)	110
(guH)[H ₂ Ce ₂ F ₁₁]	—	7.87 (7.61)	51.98 (50.86)	37.61 (37.90)	200
(biguH ₂)[HCe ₂ F ₁₁]	—	11.48 (11.80)	47.13 (47.25)	35.14 (35.22)	200
[Co(NH ₃) ₆][CeF ₆] ₂	6.70 (6.80)	9.56 (9.69)	49.14 (48.52)	33.33 (32.90)	200

py = pyridine ; en = ethylenediamine ; 2,2'-bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl ; gu = guanidine and bigu = biguanide.

the TGA of the compounds show them to be CeF₆, while the residue from the hexamminecobalt(III) compound contains the oxides of cobalt in addition. The decomposition temperatures of the compounds are shown in Table 1.

The ir spectra of the compounds in KBr show strong absorption bands in the region 380-410 cm⁻¹ due to terminal Ce-F bond¹⁰. The presence of N-H due to protonation of organic bases in the corresponding compounds is confirmed by the appearance of strong bands¹¹ at 1400-1470, 1550-1650 and 3000-3500 cm⁻¹. The presence of H₂O in the bipy-compound is confirmed¹¹ by a band at 1650 cm⁻¹.

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